

LEARNING LOOPS IN THE PUBLIC REALM

WP7. URBAN LIVING LAB - MANCHESTER
T7.1 Development of the Manchester urban living lab

Deliverable D7.1

Manchester Urban Living Lab Implementation Plan

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INTRODUCTION

This document is organised into sections corresponding to the template in D4.1. The section headings are Place, People, Priorities, Platforms and Process. Within these sections a tentative implementation plan is laid out, or in the case of stages already completed, the approach taken is described. The plan is tentative because the Manchester (Brunswick) Urban Living Lab is an emergent process. Engagement and participation are central to LOOPER and many Brunswick residents fit into categories often described as 'hard to reach'. The implementation process is thus one of coming to know the community and the diverse individuals who constitute it and learning how to engage them through dialogue and through trial and error. As a result it is difficult to present a firm detailed plan of the LOOPER stages and components.

1. PLACE

Sources of data:

- Lower Layer Super Output Areas. The smallest geographical units for which there is government data available are the Lower Layer Super Output Areas (related to multiple indices of deprivation) Manchester 018B, 018D and 018E (covering three different parts of the Brunswick neighbourhood combined with bits of other areas) and then Ward level (Ardwick) and Manchester level.
- Oxford Consultants for Social Inclusion. OCSI (www.ocsi.co.uk) produces a 'Community Outlook Report' for specific areas and specific clients using government data. S4B subscribes to these reports for Brunswick. The most recent report was from 30 May 2017.

1.1. Location, Size, Geographic Features

- Brunswick is a neighbourhood in the ward of Ardwick in the city of Manchester
- Brunswick is 0.6 km from Manchester city centre and adjacent to University of Manchester campus
- The neighbourhood is bordered by major roads on three sides
- Brunswick is a former social housing estate that was owned and managed by Manchester City Council. It is now being regenerated under a Private Finance Initiative (PFI) led by the consortium Solutions for Brunswick (S4B)
- Brunswick occupies an area of approximately 0.52 km²

Map 1 Location of Brunswick within the City of Manchester and Greater Manchester

Source: Google maps

Map 2 Location of Brunswick neighbourhood within the central area of the City of Manchester

Source: Google maps

Map 3 Brunswick Regeneration Plan showing planned layout of neighbourhood (changes are being implemented over several years – completion was scheduled for 2019)

(The area covered by the Brunswick regeneration and Manchester ULL is bounded by the red line.)

Scale of detail view: Scale 1/1250 @ A1

Source: S4B

1.2. Population and socio-economic profile

The population of Brunswick was 4,405 in 2015 according to the most recent report from the Office of National Statistics (ONS). Population characteristics are outlined in the below tables sourced from the 'Community Insight Profile for Onward Homes-Brunswick Area' (OCSI May 2017). The inhabitants are younger than the English average and the majority of the population is Black and Ethnic Minority (BME).

1.2.1. Age

Total Population	Aged 0-15	Working age population	Aged 65+	Dependency ratio
4,405	680	3,470	250	0.27
51.6% male; 48.4% female	15.5% (England average = 19.1%)	78.8% (England average = 63.3%)	5.7% (England average = 17.7%)	England average = 0.58

Source: Mid-Year Estimates (ONS) 2015

1.2.2. Ethnicity

White British	BME	White non-British	Mixed
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1,615 30.6% (England average = 79.8%)	3,660 69.4% (England average = 20.2%)	440 8.3% (England average = 5.7%)	255 4.8% (England average = 2.3%)
Asian	Black	Other ethnic group	Households with multiple ethnicities
1,790 34.0% (England average = 7.8%)	805 15.3% (England average = 3.5%)	365 6.9% (England average = 1.0%)	320 19.8% (England average = 8.9%)
Source: Census 2011			

1.2.3. Religion

1,850 35.1% (England average = 59.4%)	110 2.1% (England average = 0.5%)	110 2.0% (England average = 1.5%)	10 0.2% (England average = 0.5%)
Christian	Buddhist	Hindu	Jewish
1,175 22.3% (England average = 5.0%)	45 0.9% (England average = 0.8%)	25 0.5% (England average = 0.4%)	1,570 29.8% (England average = 24.7%)
Muslim	Sikh	Other religion	No religion
Source: Census 2011			

1.2.4. Income

The last reported average weekly household income in Brunswick was £460 (ONS, 2013/14).

1.2.5. Educational qualifications

There is a range of educational qualifications in Brunswick, which reflects the mix of people with relatively little formal education and those who are associated with the universities (both students and staff) and hospitals.

670 14.8% of working age people (England= 22.5%)	355 7.8% of working age people (England= 13.3%)	400 8.9% of working age people (England= 15.2%)	1,160 25.6% of working age people (England= 12.4%)
People with no qualifications	People with highest qualification level 1	People with highest qualification level 2	People with highest qualification level 3
1,395 30.8% of working age people (England= 27.4%)	<p>'Level 1' qualifications are equivalent to a single O-level, GCSE or NVQ. 'Level 2' qualifications are equivalent to five O-levels or GCSEs. 'Level 3' qualifications are equivalent to two A levels. 'Level 4' qualifications are equivalent to degree level or higher.</p>		
People with highest qualification level 4+ (degree)			
Source: Census 2011			

1.2.6. Type of jobs held by residents of Brunswick

Largest employment sector	Second largest employment sector	Third largest employment sector
Accommodation & food services	Retail	Health & social work
275 employees (18% of 1,475 of people in employment)	270 employees (18% of 1,475 of people in employment)	185 employees (13% of 1,475 of people in employment)

Managerial occupations	Professional (or associate) occupations	Administrative or secretarial occupations	Skilled trades occupations	Elementary occupations
65	385	145	100	310
4.3% of 1,475 people in employment (England = 10.9%)	26.3% of 1,475 people in employment (England = 30.3%)	9.9% of 1,475 people in employment (England = 11.5%)	6.7% of 1,475 people in employment (England = 11.4%)	21.0% of 1,475 people in employment (England = 11.1%)
Source: Census 2011				

Figure: People in professional and elementary occupations

Source: Census 2011

1.2.7. Overall economic activity

There are a large number of economically inactive households in Brunswick. 14% of people aged 16-74 are in full-time employment in Brunswick compared with 39% across England

Economically active	Full-time employees	Part-time employees	Self-employed people	Economically inactive
1,935	637	314	126	2,482
43.8% (England average = 69.9%)	14.4% (England average = 38.6%)	7.1% (England average = 13.7%)	2.9% (England average = 9.8%)	56.2% (England average = 30.1%)
Source: Census 2011				

Figure: Economic activity

Source: Census 2011

1.2.8. Deprived neighbourhoods - Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) 2015¹

Number of people in Onward Homes - Brunswick living in the most deprived 20% of areas of England by Indices of Deprivation (ID) 2015 domain			
Index of Multiple Deprivation	Income domain	Employment domain	Education domain
1,779	1,779	1,149	0
33.5% (England average = 20.1%)	33.5% (England average = 20.1%)	29.1% (England average = 19.7%)	-
Health domain	Barriers to Housing and Services domain	Living Environment domain	Crime domain
5,306	5,306	0	3,451
100.0% (England average = 19.8%)	100.0% (England average = 21.2%)	-	65.0% (England average = 20.6%)

Source: Communities and Local Government (Indices of Deprivation 2015)

35% of children are living in poverty in Brunswick compared with 20% across England

Children in 'out of work' households (2015)	Children in lone parent households (2012)	Children in poverty (2014)
185	375	265
27.3% (England average = 14.7%)	42.7% (England average = 27.2%)	34.6% (England average = 20.1%)

Source: HM Revenue and Customs (2012-2014), Department for Work and Pensions (2012-2014)

¹ The concept of multiple deprivation upon which the IMD 2015 is based is that separate types of deprivation exist, which are separately recognised and measurable. The IMD 2015 therefore consists of seven types, or domains, of deprivation, each of which contains a number of individual measures, or indicators. The seven domains of deprivation included are: Employment deprivation, Income deprivation, Health deprivation and disability, Education, skills and training deprivation, Crime, Living environment deprivation, Barriers to housing and services. All neighbourhoods in England are grouped into ten equal sized groups "deciles"; the 10% of neighbourhoods with the highest level of deprivation (as measured in the IMD) are grouped in decile 10, and so on with the 10% of neighbourhoods with the lowest levels of deprivation grouped in decile 1.

1.3. Density, urban form and land use mix

The population density in Brunswick is 43.6 persons/hectare. The England average is 4.1. (OCSI, 2017) Brunswick was a social housing estate built on the edge of the city centre by Manchester City Council in the late 1960s and early 1970s.

Housing is a mix of 1 and 2 bedroom flats, and 2, 3, 4 and 6 bedroom houses.

There are currently 4 multi storey blocks:

- Lamport Court: 56x1 bed flats, 8x2 bed flats
- Lockton Court: 56x1 bed flats, 8 x2 bed flats
- Silkin Court: 56x1 bed flats, 8 x2 bed flats
- Artillery Court: 50x1 bed flats, 12x 2 bed flats, 1x 3 bed flat

There are also:

- 48 Cottage flats
- 159 two bed houses
- 182 three bed houses
- 40 four bed houses
- 3 six bed houses

Tenure: Brunswick has a mixture of housing to rent on a social basis. There are also leaseholders (who own their homes but not the ground on which they stand or the exterior of multi-dwelling units). These are people who have purchased their properties under the 'Right To Buy' Scheme (government policy which allowed social housing tenants to buy the properties they rented—and sell them on if desired) and Ground Renters who have purchased a new build home. There are 87 leaseholders and 66 new build homes with ground rents.

Elizabeth Yarwood Court is a sheltered scheme for independent living for the over 60s with 30 flats in total. It is scheduled for closure and the building will be demolished. This will also result in a loss of a large garden with fruit trees and growing spaces. It is an amenity for the wider community including a LGBT youth group. It is used for community events, such as the Summer Fete led by local residents.

A small shopping plaza on Brunswick Street has recently closed down and will be demolished to make way for new sheltered housing for older people. New shops are being developed on the Eastern edge of the neighbourhood and S4B's new office is now located here. A health centre and pharmacy are located next to the shops. On the Western edge there is a large Chinese supermarket (wholesale and retail) and adjoining restaurant. Next to this and also facing outwards to the main road are two high end car salesrooms. There is one industrial building on the Northern edge of the neighbourhood, which houses small manufacturers and warehouses, and a number of smaller buildings also serving commercial purposes in the surrounding area. According to a local resident/community leader who has undertaken an inventory, there are an estimated 38 businesses located in Brunswick. There are three community facilities: Brunswick Church, the Salvation Army and the Wai Yin Society (the focus of the latter is Manchester and North West England rather than Brunswick). There is one school, Medlock Primary School. The two pubs in the neighbourhood have closed (one quite recently and one some time ago) and the buildings that housed them are derelict.

1.4. Infrastructure

The neighbourhood is bordered by a raised urban expressway, the Mancunian Way, to the North and by major roads on the East and West.

From the Northern edge of the neighbourhood it is a ten minute walk to either Oxford Road Station or Manchester Piccadilly Station which link Manchester with local services and intercity routes.

1.5.Environment

The presence of the major roads described above means that air quality is an important issue in the neighbourhood. Four pollutants have been observed to be present at higher levels than the England average.

Benzene concentrations	Nitrogen Dioxide concentrations	Particulates (PM10) concentrations	Sulphur Dioxide concentrations
0.13	0.9	0.5	0.08
(England average = 0.09)	(England average = 0.5)	(England average = 0.4)	(England average = 0.05)

Source: Communities and Local Government (Indices of Deprivation 2015 - from National Air Quality Archive 2012)

1.6.Local Governance

Brunswick is part of Ardwick ward within Manchester City Council and Greater Manchester. Ardwick has three Councillors, all of whom take an interest in the Brunswick neighbourhood. There is a Tenants and Residents Association (TARA) that was created to provide a forum for citizens to raise issues but a number of residents feel that the Brunswick TARA does not play this role effectively.

1.7.Regeneration/renewal/development

£113M is being invested in regeneration of the Brunswick neighbourhood. The Brunswick Regeneration Private Finance Initiative (PFI) combines government funding with private investment and expertise in development, housing and finance ('blending private investment with not-for-profit values' as stated on S4B website). Improvements include council home refurbishments, new homes for sale and to rent and an improved neighbourhood design. To secure the funding needed, the Council has created a partnership. S4B is a consortium of companies put together specifically for this scheme. S4B is responsible for making improvements and managing the neighbourhood including housing services for 25 years (beginning in 2013).

The S4B team is managed by the lead and independent investor Equitix. Construction specialist Galliford Try is building all of the new roads, new landscaping and facilities and also building new homes for sale and to rent. Another company, Mears, is refurbishing the existing homes and providing the repairs and maintenance services across the council properties for the next 25 years. Contour Homes/Onward will be managing the council housing and other neighbourhood services for the length of the contract.

Regeneration timelines: Resident consultation started in 2006; S4B signed the contract in Summer 2013; public information events took place in 2013 and the work began in Autumn of that year.

New roads, refurbishment and new build social homes were scheduled for completion at the end of 2017 but in mid-2018 much remains to be done.

Expected results:

- 1,361 new or refurbished units, providing more family housing, offering greater choice and exceeding the Decent Homes Standards (minimum standard council and housing association homes should meet according to the government); 650 homes refurbished, 124 houses reversed (where back doors become front doors and the house connects to a road rather than a footpath as before)
- Employment of local trainees and creation of 295 local labour opportunities across the lifetime of the project
- Demolition of 296 unsatisfactory homes (elsewhere S4B states 270 homes are being demolished and replaced with 200 new social rent homes, and 322 homes for sale)
- New S4B (Onward) housing office and new retail space
- New extra-care housing scheme

- New infrastructure and road layouts with better east-west / north-south linkages and legible vehicle, bus, cycle and pedestrian routes
- Improvements to the main park (Gartside Gardens) and new play spaces
- Allotments (food growing spaces assigned to local residents) and a community orchard

1.8. Other – Important community spaces

- Brunswick Church
- Medlock Primary School
- Salvation Army
- Gartside Gardens
- Cornbrook Green Space
- Elizabeth Yarwood Close gardens

N.B. The Wai Yin Society is also housed in the neighbourhood but its focus is Manchester wide and regional rather than on Brunswick

1.9. Other – Crime and safety

The overall crime rate in Brunswick is higher than the average across England.

Recorded Crime:

All crimes March 2017 monthly total	All crimes Jan17-Mar17	All crimes Apr16-Mar17
187	491	1,834
45 per 1,000 population (England average = 10)	119 per 1,000 population (England average = 28)	434.9 per 1,000 population (England average = 112.8)
Violent crimes Apr16-Mar17	Criminal damage incidents Apr16-Mar17	Anti-social behaviour incidents Apr16-Mar17
318	100	523
72.2 per 1,000 population (England average = 21.1)	17.3 per 1,000 population (England average = 9.6)	118.8 per 1,000 population (England average = 31.0)
Burglaries Apr16-Mar17	Robberies Apr16-Mar17	Vehicle crimes Apr16-Mar17
64	57	97
38.5 per 1,000 households (England average = 16.8)	12.9 per 1,000 population (England average = 1.0)	26.1 per 1,000 population (England average = 7.1)
Source: Recorded crime offences – www.police.uk (2017)		

2. PEOPLE

2.1. Community and other stakeholders

Brunswick has an ethnically diverse population which comes together in a variety of different groups (some of which are more representative of the diversity than others) including: the Brunswick Tenants and Residents Association (TARA); parents of children at Medlock Primary School who participate in various activities at the school and children involved in the school's Eco-Club; Brunswick Women's group; Chorlton-on-Medlock Allotment Society (COMAS); a group of people interested in green spaces that receives some support (facilitation and training) from the City Council; Elizabeth Yarwood Close (seniors residence and drop in centre); children and parents who meet at the Salvation

Army youth club and participate in activities offered to them there; and the University-Ardwick partnership (UAP). There are also regular community events taking place at Brunswick Church, Medlock School and occasionally the Salvation Army.

Non-resident stakeholders include: S4B, Manchester City Council, Transport for Greater Manchester, City of Trees and the University of Manchester (all of these organisations are potential facilitators of interventions, policymakers and learners in the LOOPER process).

2.1.1. Hard to reach groups

Members of Brunswick’s diverse population speak a number of different languages and can be hard to reach for this reason (or expensive to reach because it is costly to produce materials and undertake outreach in the range of languages present).

Initial experience within the Brunswick Urban Living lab indicates that it is easiest (in relative terms) to reach ethnically diverse (with the exception of the Chinese community) women of different ages, level of education and family situation; people with mental health problems; a sample of car owners and non car owners; and men playing leadership roles in the community. It is more difficult to reach the sizeable Chinese community; men more broadly (those who are not playing local leadership roles); people with physical disabilities; and youth.

There are a number of reasons why some groups may be harder to reach: Women tend to be generally more active than men in neighbourhood level community spaces, and this is accentuated in Brunswick by the influence of Muslim traditions where many activities are divided by gender--so that when women organise activities they are less likely to include men. The Chinese community is traditionally less engaged with the wider community (we have unsuccessfully reached out to some of its members). Temporary residents (e.g. students and families of students) tend not to be invested in the neighbourhood because they know they will move on. More middle class people also tend not to engage very much perhaps because they are more connected to things beyond the neighbourhood, or do not see themselves as members of a community where social housing dominates.

Country of birth, passport and language

Born in England	Born Outside the UK	With a UK passport	With a non-UK passport
2,495	2,625	2,895	1,960
47.3% (England average = 83.5%)	49.8% (England average = 13.8%)	54.9% (England average = 75.8%)	37.2% (England average = 8.8%)
All people in households have English as main language	At least one adult (not all) has English as main language	No adults but some children have English as main language	No household members have English as main language
1,000	140	75	400
61.9% (England average = 90.9%)	8.7% (England average = 3.9%)	4.5% (England average = 0.8%)	24.9% (England average = 4.4%)
Source: Census 2011			

2.1.2. Migration

The large number of people who are new to the neighbourhood and/or unlikely to stay long (such as students) can mean that people are hard to reach and/or less likely to engage with the community.

People who have moved address within the last 12 months (Census 2011)	Overseas migrants (National Insurance no. registrations of overseas nationals) (DWP 2015/16)
2,240	255

2.1.3. Household composition

There is a large percentage of single person households in Brunswick, which may signal social isolation and indicate a sector of the population who might benefit from engaging the community but also be potentially hard to reach.

Pensioner households	One person households (aged under 65)	Lone parent families with dependent children
145	565	155
9.0% (England average = 20.7%)	35.2% (England average = 17.9%)	35.1% of all families with dependent children (England average = 24.5%)
Married households	Cohabiting households	Student households
290	90	120
17.9% (England average = 33.2%)	5.7% (England average = 9.8%)	7.3% (England average = 0.6%)
Source: Census 2011		

Figure: Population by household composition

Source: Census 2011

There were 120 households of one pensioner in 2011 (Census 2011). This represents 82.2% of pensioner households (England average = 59.6%).

170 people in Brunswick are receiving mental health related benefits (DWP, 2016)

Overall the community is hard to reach because it is characterised by communication barriers, mistrust and a tendency toward disengagement resulting from experiences of marginalisation and lack of voice in the public sphere.

2.2. Engagement strategy for stakeholders

There are many languages spoken in the neighbourhood and a lack of resources to directly address people in this range of languages; we only produce material in English. People are however encouraged to use their languages and to assist others.

With respect to outreach, we find that word of mouth is most effective and thus rely heavily on this means of communication. Verbal exchanges can be accompanied by handing out LOOPER postcards, which provide brief information and contact details---and hopefully increase recognition of LOOPER. We also communicate by email and text. We rely on partner S4B for broader communication as they have communication links with all residents and maintain a website and social media.

A lot of people need to be encouraged to come along to activities by trusted others. We endeavour to develop trust with residents and also to build good relationship with key actors who are trusted by residents.

Rather than organising specific LOOPER activities, we try to go to people where they are and when they are already meeting. An important part of our strategy involves being present in the neighbourhood, participating in events and activities, bringing LOOPER information and activities to popular venues.

We recognise the need to take an iterative approach. This means continuing to explore what people are concerned about and also what sort of things they are interested in learning and doing that might be incorporated into LOOPER. We will continue to adapt our approach as we move through the LOOPER stages. This sort of adaptive experimentation seems appropriate within a living lab.

2.3. Other – Health and Wellbeing

The life expectancy in Brunswick is below the average in other social housing areas as well as the average in England.

Life Expectancy, Office for National Statistics (2010/11-2013/14)

Healthy Life Expectancy, Office for National Statistics (2009-2013)

Number of people in each deprivation decile, Health domain (Indices of Deprivation 2015)

2.1. Other – Neighbourhood satisfaction and participation

The percentage of people ‘satisfied with their neighbourhood’ in Brunswick is lower (70%) than the average across England. In parallel 34% of people in Brunswick ‘believe they can influence local decisions’.

Neighbourhood satisfaction and local participation

months	local area	the last 12 months	
15%	34%	20%	1.8 per 1,000 population
(England = 14%)	(England = 29%)	(England = 23%)	(England = 2.6 per 1,000)
Source: Place Survey (2008), Active Charities - National Council for Voluntary Organisations (NCVO) (2009). Note all information is collected at Local Authority level			

3. PRIORITIES

3.1. Tangible priorities

The following issues (listed more or less in order of importance) have been identified as priorities.

3.1.1. Air quality

Brunswick residents are concerned about air quality because the neighbourhood is surrounded by major roads and the two through roads in the neighbourhood are heavily used by commuters. Residents also complain that non-residents (often students or employees of neighbouring universities and hospitals) drive around the neighbourhood looking for parking. Some parents are worried about high rates of asthma among children. Concern about air quality may have increased due to recent media coverage about poor air quality in Manchester.

3.1.2. Traffic volume and road safety

The traffic described above is also linked to complaints about the volume of traffic moving through the neighbourhood and the speed with which it moves. This is seen as both a safety concern and an irritation. There have been a considerable number of complaints about various parking related issues. As well as traffic created by non-residents, resident traffic may increase as additional houses have been added to neighbourhood and both new and old houses are being newly provided with driveways. N.B. Brunswick has traditionally been characterised by low car ownership. In 2011 66% of households had no car in Brunswick compared with 26% across England (2011 Census). More roads have been built for access to houses, some of which were previously accessed primarily by footpaths. Some of the new roads facilitate access from the main roads surrounding the neighbourhood.

3.1.3. Community spaces/amenities

People are concerned about the lack of good community spaces and other amenities. This is related to the relocation of some amenities (particularly shops) and the loss of places such as a laundrette, a fish and chip shop and some green spaces.

3.1.4. Nature in the landscape

In addition to the loss of green spaces, the loss of trees and gardens that have been paved over for driveways and/or 'easier maintenance' are mentioned by residents.

3.1.5. Feeling safe and secure

People in many parts of Brunswick say that they feel safe in their areas of the neighbourhood. Some however do complain about feelings of insecurity particularly if they find themselves in proximity to groups of people engaged in substance abuse.

3.1.6. Noise

Some mention was made of traffic noise, particularly from the Mancunian Way. While others said that they got used to it. Noise from construction activities associated with the regeneration process was also mentioned.

3.2. Structural factors

Many of the concerns in Brunswick are related to or have surfaced as a result of the regeneration process, which is seen to have made changes that go against people's wishes. The regeneration includes aspects of gentrification and some people in Brunswick feel resentful of the new housing for sale, which is seen to be of better quality and with the best locations, particularly that located across from Gartside Gardens, which was slightly reduced in area (and trees) in order to make room for a new 'boulevard' running in front of the houses.

3.3. Identification of key issues

Air quality, traffic volume and safety, community spaces and greening have been identified as key issues.

4. PLATFORMS

4.1. Online tools

LOOPER staff are encouraging Brunswick residents to use monitoring and visualisation tools related to geotagging and air quality monitoring. These include the geotagging application developed by IUAV with results made available for viewing on the LOOPER website. We are using Airbeam2 monitors and the corresponding Aircasting platform to record air quality (particulate) measurements. Data collected through the latter will be processed by IUAV with results made available on the LOOPER website. In the co-design phase, we will collect and display ideas online using the Wordpress theme NextSeventeen by NextHamburg, which is being adapted for LOOPER.

4.2. Offline tools

The Brunswick residents who get involved in neighbourhood activities (and are consequently most likely to engage with the LOOPER process) do not appear to make extensive use of online tools. Offline spaces and tools are therefore very important in the Brunswick context. Brunswick is a relatively small primarily residential neighbourhood where it is easy to meet people on the streets and speak to them. Being seen in the neighbourhood is important to build familiarity and trust and walking around with community members known to local residents is a good way to get to know people and their concerns. There are few community spaces but Brunswick Church is the venue for many meetings and events, and also has a café like area and provides community meals twice a week. Spending time in this space and participating in meetings and events is important to develop a LOOPER presence and learn about issues of concern.

A lack of online engagement and an apparent desire to engage in face-to-face activities has encouraged us to seek offline tools for use in Brunswick. We have used Ketso (www.ketso.com), a kit to support collaborative thinking, planning, decision-making and other functions. Ketso is designed to include every voice around the table and also offers an easy way to capture, collate and organise people's ideas. We have also explored how to bring online tools offline (and then hopefully to put the results back online). While getting people to use the geotagging tool is a challenge, people have engaged more readily with offline maps, particularly large format printouts of Google Earth views of the neighbourhood. We are also looking at using 3D photos of key sites of concern in the neighbourhood in

workshops where people will view the photos projected on walls and together discuss and annotate them (e.g. on flipchart paper onto which the images are projected).

4.3.Data

Our data collection is focused on air quality, traffic volume and speed, and perceptions of specific places in the neighbourhood. Data collection activities include geotagging, air quality monitoring, traffic counts and speed monitoring.

Air quality in Brunswick is primarily linked to traffic, and particularly to the volume of traffic moving around and through the neighbourhood. Therefore, our air quality monitoring, traffic counting and speed monitoring focuses primarily on these busy roads at peak traffic times (morning, evening and afternoon school run). In order to carry out this monitoring we decided purchase two Airbeam2 monitors and were able to borrow six traffic speed monitors from Manchester City Council. We would have liked to monitor air quality in relation to NO² and CO but were not able to obtain or construct the suggested monitor. (We have been trying with support from Manchester Friends of the Earth to collaborate in test tube monitoring of NO² at Medlock Primary School and integrate this process and the results into LOOPER activities.) We are able to give context to our own monitoring by accessing publicly available data from two government air quality monitoring stations located near Brunswick.

Our key challenge with respect to data collection is the lack of enthusiasm about monitoring on the part of most Brunswick residents. This raises questions about different approaches we might try to engage them in the monitoring process and also whether we should instead focus on other activities that do interest them.

5. PROCESS - IMPLEMENTATION

The first stage of implementation involved the inception of the living lab and scoping of problems. As mentioned earlier, the Brunswick ULL implementation process has been emergent, involving coming to know the community and learning how to engage them and collaborate with them through trying out different activities and forms of interaction. In keeping with the emergent process, some of the stages overlap and some activities contribute to fulfilling the objectives of more than one stage. The Manchester LOOPER Lab is now established, and the sections below detail the process and activities that were undertaken to set it up.

5.1.Set up

15 September 2017 marked the inception of the Brunswick LOOPER Lab when the S4B Community Development Officer and Community Regeneration Officer and UoM Research Associate met at the offices of S4B to plan the engagement and problem identification processes. Discussions began here about communications and outreach activities, which got started the following week.

Discussions with S4B and other organisations active in the area made it clear that Brunswick is not the sort of place where you can announce a meeting about problems in the public realm and expect more than a handful of people to attend. The community is characterised by communication barriers, mistrust and a tendency toward disengagement resulting from experiences of marginalisation and lack of voice in the public sphere. In this context we needed to seek out intermediary individuals and organisations that have a recognised role in the community, existing relationships of trust and knowledge of how to reach the segments of the community with whom they work. We then set out to try to integrate LOOPER activities as much as possible with existing activities.

The role of S4B was very important in this process. S4B is the embodiment of the Private Finance Initiative (PFI) that has taken over management from local government of the former social housing estate of Brunswick, which it is in the process of 'regenerating'. S4B is not necessarily seen as a trusted friend given the significant changes taking place and associated disturbance, hostility toward the perceived privatisation of the estate and persistent problems in the neighbourhood. S4B is however

seen by residents as a primary actor with the power to effect change in Brunswick. Furthermore, as the social landlord or lessor (for leaseholders who have purchased their properties) S4B has information about and the means to contact most residents in the neighbourhood. An important role is also played by the Community Development Officer (who has an explicit role in LOOPER and joined S4B when LOOPER began). She quickly established an extensive network and a reputation for being accessible, helpful and proactive. This has contributed significantly to LOOPER's capacity for community outreach and relationship building.

5.1.1. Local Community Outreach

Communications work included development (with the assistance of the S4B Communications officer) of a postcard and poster for LOOPER Brunswick. (These were printed before the LOOPER logo was available but the logo was added to subsequent material.) A LOOPER Brunswick Facebook page was also created but this has not been used because it was decided that the existing communication channels, particularly the S4B Facebook page and text messages, would be more effective.

Through our interactions we realised that we needed a simple one page description of the LOOPER project that we could share with Brunswick residents and other stakeholders (see Appendix 1). This 'What is LOOPER?' document misrepresents the LOOPER loops to some extent by presenting a connected series of loops signifying the stages of the community learning loop. But people found it helpful and said that it gave them a better understanding of the LOOPER project. The 'What is LOOPER' sheet is being updated to communicate different stages of the project.

With respect to community outreach, the following activities were undertaken:

1. Informal interactions: with Brunswick community members at local activities, most notably, regular participation in Tuesday and Thursday community lunches and spending time at the church hall, which is the key meeting place in Brunswick (regardless of people's religious affiliations).

Introductions by other local actors helped to facilitate these interactions. Colleagues from UoM's Brunswick Anchor programme/University Ardwick Partnership, which is part of University's social responsibility initiative, played a helpful role, as did Manchester City Council and the Community Resources Manager at Brunswick Church. (along with other facilitators of the women's group).

2. *Being out on the streets*: in particular participating in several neighbourhood walkabouts, including the monthly 'estate walkabout' with S4B, Manchester City Council (MCC) and local residents. These walkabouts are a good opportunity to hear from both the people participating in the walk and those they speak to along the way about local issues. S4B's school run safety watches, which ensure that parents do not stop their cars in the no stopping zone in front of the school, provides lots of opportunities to speak with parents about local issues particularly concerning road safety and parking.

3. *Participation in meetings of local groups* to introduce LOOPER and have informal discussions about issues of local concern. Such meetings took place with the following groups:

- 4 October 2017 - Brunswick Tenants and Residents Association (TARA)
- 6 October 2017 - Parents Coffee Morning at Medlock Primary School (which was also an opportunity to interact with teaching staff)
- 16 October 2017 - Brunswick Women's group
- 17 October 2017 - Chorlton-on-Medlock Allotment Society (COMAS)
- 3 November 2017 - Elizabeth Yarwood Close (seniors residence and drop in centre) community lunch
- 28 February 2018 - Medlock Primary School Eco-Club

Efforts were made at this stage to set up meetings with the local youth group (M13) and the Wai Yin Society (organisation run by Chinese women providing services to minority communities in the North West of England). We were not able to schedule anything during the initial stages although some connections were made with youth group later on.

4. *Participation in community events*: We had a LOOPER stall at the 'Brunswick Bonanza' information and activity day held on 7 November. This provided an excellent opportunity to interact with various members of the community and provide information about LOOPER verbally and via postcards and the one-page information sheet. We also used our kiosk to try out Ketso, a participatory discussion and idea mapping tool (see below) which we thought we might use as a key tool for identifying issues. The 13 January S4B birthday and Masterplan consultation and the 19 February Youth Provision Launch at the Salvation Army building were other key engagement events.

5. *Efforts to engage residents beyond the usual suspects*: We wanted to seize opportunities to engage the broadest group of residents possible, including those who were unlikely to show an interest in a project like LOOPER. We were open to exploring a range of ideas, including a fashion show.

Involvement in the array of activities described above allowed us to develop a network of relationships that brought together a range of residents reflecting different areas of the neighbourhood, demographic characteristics and interests. The network was extended by always asking people to tell others about LOOPER or to suggest other people or groups with whom we could connect. As a result of these activities we identified some emerging LOOPER volunteers/community researchers. We hoped to be able to establish a core group of people who would become particularly engaged in LOOPER, contribute to orienting the process overall and/or take responsibility for implementation and monitoring of interventions. We wanted and would still like to explore the possibility of offering people a stipend for this work. Particular people have engaged more deeply but this has remained quite informal. Having these people come together explicitly as a group of LOOPER community researchers has not made sense because sub-group cultures are quite different and there is also quite a bit of conflict among actively engaged individuals.

The question of conflicts within the local community adds a particular challenge to engaging local residents with LOOPER. There are some individuals who feel strongly that they are the key actors and designated representatives of the Brunswick community and this sometimes means that they block access to other community actors or potential actors. This means that considerable effort is required to reach beyond more outspoken individuals and groups to those whose presence is less visible, and to

do this in a way that does not exacerbate conflicts. We have tried to proceed carefully and thoughtfully and to build and maintain relationships with as many people as possible.

5.1.2. Outreach to other stakeholders

We also sought to develop relationships with stakeholders and potential partners who were not local residents in order to identify potential partners to help deliver the LOOPER interventions and also organisations who may be able to learn from them. A key stakeholder and partner is Manchester City Council (MCC) and we have endeavoured to reach out and develop relationships with both staff and Councillors. We are now collaborating with MCC in Council-led activities (e.g. Active Streets) and LOOPER activities (e.g. MAMCA workshop).

A local organisation, City of Trees, is working in collaboration with MCC, UoM Estates and Arup to improve green infrastructure in Brunswick. We met with these collaborators on 20 October 2017 and again on 14 February 2018. Learning what these groups are doing and building relationships with them lays the groundwork for a range of potential interventions that respond to the issues that have begun to be identified.

5.2. Problem Identification

The process of problem identification began during the outreach activities described above. During the formal Problem Identification stage we undertook more systematic data gathering that sought to include more people's voices and to give us a better sense of the prevalence of particular concerns and more clearly identify specific sites of interest. To this end, we used a pre-existing field-tested participatory tool and also improvised activities that we thought might be effective.

5.2.1. Participatory tools and activities

Ketso (Ketso.com) is a workshop kit in a bag that gives everyone a voice and allows groups to organise their ideas and to record the outcomes. We piloted its use for LOOPER in a workshop format on 13 November 2017 with the Brunswick Women's Group and it was well received. This sort of group process is how Ketso is mainly used but we ended up primarily using it at stalls during events to get individual input. We soon realised that the well-designed and colourful Ketso kits drew people's attention and encouraged their engagement more than similar processes using less attractive materials.

We started using large Google Earth printouts and putting these up during LOOPER activities (particularly the LOOPER stalls at events) and found that people were very attracted to these. We had images from two different times, which showed how the neighbourhood was evolving during the regeneration. Unfortunately, we did not have a fully up to date image showing current issues but at the same time it was useful to remind people of what had been and stimulate reflections on the changes. We sometimes used the satellite images in conjunction with Ketso so that people could link their comments about issues to places on the maps (using corresponding numbers written on Ketso leaves and dots stuck on the map). This allowed us to combine thematic and spatial information. When we reached a point where there was a lot of repetition in descriptions of issues of concern, we reduced our use of Ketso and prepared a one-page sheet where people could identify and make notes about places on the maps (see Appendix 2). We also used these sheets without the actual map when it was more convenient e.g. when attending meetings of different groups. Throughout all of this, there were always people who just wanted to talk (sometimes stimulated by the satellite images) rather than filling in a form or writing things on Ketso leaves so we also tried to note what was said in these exchanges.

We were interested in the online/offline opportunities of Ketso and the satellite maps when these are combined with geotagging. While some people in Brunswick are less interested or comfortable in entering information online, we are able to transfer their input to the virtual maps and similarly share what is on the virtual maps by describing it to them and/or making printouts of the virtual map.

Another tool that we are interested in using with support from partner Clicks and Links is 360° photos of areas in Brunswick where there are particular issues of concern. We are exploring projecting these images on the walls during a meeting (and giving participants 3D glasses to view them) and then asking people present in the room to post comments or ideas on the images; and then digitalising this input and making the tagged pictures available online where further input would be invited from a larger group of people. This represents another online/offline approach, which we now see as a potentially interesting component of the co-design stage. We currently have the set of relevant photos and these are linked to a map of Brunswick and viewable on the LOOPER Manchester platform.

Key events in problem scoping:

- 7 Nov - LOOPER kiosk at the 'Brunswick Bonanza' information and activity day. Initial distribution of LOOPER postcards and 'What is LOOPER?' handouts; use of Ketso for problem identification
- 13 Nov - Workshop with Brunswick Women's Group using Ketso with 15 participants
- 13 Jan - S4B birthday celebration and master plan consultation; Ketso and Google Earth printout used for problem identification
- 19 February - Brunswick Youth Provision Launch at Salvation Army; Ketso and Google Earth printout used for problem identification
- 21 April - 'Celebrating Past, Present and Future' at Brunswick Church; Google Earth printouts used with form for identification of important sites/issues

5.2.2. Problems identified

By early 2018 we had identified three main areas of concern that were dominant within the input from residents: (1) traffic safety; (2) air quality; (3) community spaces (green spaces and other shared spaces and services). We began to discuss these emerging priorities with residents and other

stakeholders to check for general agreement while also continuing to ask people about their concerns and getting more details about these.

Air quality is primarily linked to traffic, and particularly to the volume of traffic moving around and through the neighbourhood. There is a lot of concern about through traffic related to 'rat runs' (use by commuters to avoid traffic on other roads) and about parking by university and hospital employees. There are particular concerns about children's health with reference to high rates of asthma.

Traffic safety is linked to the volume of traffic and to behaviours and practices of drivers, as well as to how pedestrians and cyclists move about the area and where children play or how people otherwise use community spaces. We want to identify spaces and routes of concern and monitor behaviours in these areas.

Community spaces include green spaces, which may have an effect on air quality and other health and wellbeing concerns. Issues related to community spaces include the presence of necessary amenities (e.g. laundrette, shops) and quality spaces in the neighbourhood and also access to those a bit further afield. Brunswick is surrounded by amenities in the city centre and on the university campus but residents don't necessarily see these as part of their patch or take full advantage of them.

In order to confirm and refine the problems there was not a single forum we could report back to, so we had to report and verify through a variety of means:

- Listing issues emerging on site/issue identification handout (See Appendix 2)
- Updated version of 'What is LOOPER?' sheet (See Appendix 1)
- Presentations at meetings e.g. Tenants and Residents Association (Powerpoint posted in Looper Sharepoint), Parents at Youth Club, Women's Group
- Informal discussions
- Participatory sensing information sheet (See Appendix 3)

At the end of January 2018 we felt confident that the three identified areas of concern were widely shared by Brunswick residents. We then began to think about how we might learn more about them.

5.3. Data collection

During the data collection phase we sought to engage residents in gathering data concerning air quality, traffic volume and speed, as well as perceptions of specific places in the neighbourhood. Data collection activities include geotagging, air quality monitoring, traffic counts and speed monitoring.

5.3.1. Identifying existing data

Our effort to locate air quality and traffic data for Brunswick focused on Manchester-I (www.manchester-i.com), Triangulum (www.triangulum-project.eu); and the UK Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (Defra) air quality data for Manchester (http://www.airqualityengland.co.uk/site/latest?site_id=MAN1).

5.3.2. Preparing for Data collection

We met with UoM air quality experts early in 2018 to get their input. They warned us about the inaccuracy of the relatively inexpensive handheld monitors suitable for citizen participation. We took heed of their concerns and noted the possibility of calibrating our monitors with the Defra monitors mentioned above.

A Clicks and Links colleague provided a demonstration of the Airbeam monitor and described his experiences of using it in a citizen science project in Liverpool. We explored the possibility of purchasing both Airbeam and the somewhat cheaper Plume Flow. We decided against the latter because it was a newly developed product that would not be available until at least June 2018. We purchased two newly released Airbeam2 monitors from HabitatMap. We borrowed one Android

phone from UoM, which we also offered to citizens for geotagging. LOOPER and S4B staff used personal phones for these purposes.

We also looked into the possibility of building NO² monitors and were hopeful that the M13 youth group might be able to incorporate this into a new science project but this was not feasible.

Manchester City Council lent us six traffic speed monitors and VUB provided us with recommendations for traffic counting tools/apps and examples of protocols.

We as LOOPER staff familiarised ourselves with using the air quality monitors and the corresponding aircasting app as well as the geotagging app, speed monitors and traffic counting apps. We were then ready to start using the equipment with residents.

We had noted problem areas in the neighbourhood during the problem identification stage. With respect to traffic safety and air quality these were essentially the same, i.e.:

- the two through streets used by commuters i.e. Brunswick Street and Grosvenor Street
- the area around Medlock Primary School
- the main roads at the western and eastern edges of the neighbourhood i.e. Upper Brook Street and A6
- (with respect to air quality) the areas close to the Mancunian Way elevated motorway at the northern edge of the neighbourhood

We determined that we should direct our monitoring efforts to these areas. While focusing on mobile monitoring walks with residents, we also wanted to do some fixed monitoring in residents' homes that are next to the major roads but were discouraged from doing this sort of fixed monitoring.

5.3.3. Participatory Sensing

We began outreach in May 2018 concerning the opportunities for Brunswick residents to get involved in monitoring activities. We took information about the monitors (see, for example, the information sheet in Appendix 3) and the monitors themselves to community events and meetings. We demonstrated use of the monitors and corresponding online tools. We invited residents to engage (with our support) in three elements of participatory sensing:

Geotagging: We offered Brunswick residents access (creation of personal login) to the crowdmapping portal so that they could use it on their own phones. We also offered training to use the crowdmapping app and opportunities to do the monitoring together with LOOPER staff. Later we sent a 'Resident' login via email to people who had expressed in interest in the LOOPER project and who had given us their email addresses.

Air quality monitoring: We offered residents opportunities to undertake monitoring accompanied by LOOPER staff and subsequently on their own if desired (in the case of trusted individuals prepared to take responsibility for looking after monitors).

Traffic monitoring: We similarly offered residents opportunities to undertake speed monitoring and traffic counting accompanied by LOOPER staff and subsequently on their own if desired.

There was less interest than we had hoped in the monitoring activities and some residents that had expressed interest did not participate when the agreed time arrived. There was more interest in doing the monitoring with LOOPER staff than in going out alone.

In an effort to drum up more enthusiasm we announced September 2018 as LOOPER monitoring month. We said that LOOPER staff would be going out to do the monitoring at peak traffic times and we invited residents to get in touch if they wanted to join us. See announcement in Appendix 4, which was sent by email to all residents who had expressed interest in the LOOPER project. The announcement was also printed up and distributed at key community venues.

With respect to monitoring air quality, we focused on monitoring in the areas listed above on Tuesday, Wednesday and Thursday during peak hours (8-9; 4-5/5-6) plus 3-3.30 pm around the school--and other hours when opportunities arose. One resident who lives near the Mancunian Way took

responsibility for monitoring in this area at various times of day. LOOPER staff did air quality monitoring regardless of whether residents participated.

The traffic monitoring was more difficult because it required more than one person to do it effectively and often the LOOPER staff member was alone during any sort of monitoring. We took advantage of the visit to Manchester of a VUB colleague (who we presented as an ‘international traffic monitoring expert’) to try to drum up interest in traffic monitoring activities at the hours indicated above during the last week of September. (See Appendix 5 for announcement sent by email and distributed at key venues.) Three residents participated. One of them and another resident volunteered to hold onto the speed monitors and take some more measurements. We will follow up with them in October.

It was very difficult to get people involved with geotagging. Residents did not take initiative to do it on their own. A few were willing to walk around with LOOPER staff and point out places that could be entered on the map.

We have now completed the data collection phase but will continue to provide monitoring opportunities if citizens are interested.

5.4. Summary of completed stages

The table below summarises the process of setting up the Manchester ULL, scoping/problem identification and data collection. It includes details of the timescales and who has been involved at each stage.

<i>Action</i>	<i>Goals</i>	<i>Key activities and responsibilities</i>	<i>Date</i>
Inception of LOOPER Lab	To plan engagement processes. To plan problem identification processes.	Formal meeting (UoM and S4B).	15/09/17
Local community engagement	To publicise LOOPER. To establish community involvement in the LOOPER Lab.	Informal interactions with Brunswick community members at local activities (UoM and S4B). Participation in monthly neighbourhood walkabouts (S4B and UoM). Participation in meetings of local groups including Brunswick Tenants and Residents Association, Parents Coffee morning at Medlock Primary School Brunswick Women’s group, Chorlton-on-Medlock Allotment Society, Elizabeth Yarwood Close (seniors residence and drop in centre), and Medlock Primary School Eco-Club (S4B and UoM)	19/09/17 – 26/06/18
Scope problems	To broadly identify key public realm concerns across the community.	Workshops with specific community groups including Brunswick Women’s Group and Brunswick Youth Provision (UoM and S4B). LOOPER kiosk at key stakeholder events held by S4B and Brunswick Church (UoM and S4B).	07/11/17 – 21/04/18
Stakeholder engagement	To engage key organisations into co-design of Looper Lab. To secure delivery partners and harness local capabilities.	Meetings with wider project partners including Manchester City Council including Neighbourhoods Team and Brunswick Councillors, S4B wider staff and the University Ardwick Partnership (UoM, S4B, Manchester City Council). Developing relationships with local delivery partners already working on public realm improvements in Ardwick,	20/10/17 -

	To establish basis for policy learning loops.	including City of Trees, Manchester City Council, UoM Estates and Arup (UoM and S4B). Develop plan for engaging key organisations who are intended to learn from the LOOPER interventions (UoM, S4B and Manchester City Council).	
Mapping existing data	To capture existing data that describes the area. To capture existing data that describes the key problems.	Identify and review online and publicly available sources of data at national, regional and local levels, held by public, private and third sector bodies (UoM and S4B). Contact key stakeholder organisations to identify further sector specific data sets (UoM, S4B and Manchester City Council). Use final year and masters students to help identify data sources and fill data gaps through small projects (UoM).	20/09/17 - 21/04/18
Preparing for data collection	Engaging the community with the process of data collection. Identifying data that can be collected. Preparing a data collection strategy.	Visit existing community groups and events to present community monitoring possibilities around air quality, traffic speed and noise (UoM and S4B) and identify what they want to monitor. Meet with experts to identify best equipment and training techniques (UoM and CL). Develop a data collection strategy that sets out sampling frameworks for key variables and allocated monitoring to community volunteers. Adapt this strategy as required (UoM and S4B).	25/01/18 - 21/09/18
Data collection	Invite residents to collect data and provide them with the support required. Collect useful data that clarifies the nature of problems. Facilitate participatory sensing through which residents learn more about the issues that concern them.	Set up opportunities for residents to collect data (UoM and S4B). Furnish the necessary equipment and support to participants. (UoM) Experiment with different approaches to engage residents in monitoring activities (UoM and S4B). In the absence of resident participation, collect some data in order to test LOOPER processes (UoM). Ensure that data is uploaded to the appropriate platform (UoM) to be retrieved by IUAV. Review data collected and prepare the groundwork for the next stages.	15/05/18 – 29/09/18

5.5. Implementation plan and timetable for remaining stages

The table below gives a summary of key implementation activities, with dates & responsibilities, for the Manchester LOOPER Lab from October 2018 to the end of the project.

<i>Stage of implementation</i>	<i>Key activities and responsibilities</i>	<i>Dates</i>
Data synthesis and visualisation (Learning Loop 1)	<p>Visualisations of collected data will be published on the LOOPER platform for each living lab and discussed at local workshops (IAUV, UoM).</p> <p>We will encourage stakeholders to go online and also use printouts and Powerpoint slides of geotagging and air quality maps in presentations at meetings of Brunswick community groups (UoM, S4B).</p>	Oct. – Nov. 2018
Co-design and evaluation of alternative solutions (Learning Loop 1)	<p>During the presentations to community groups mentioned above, we will encourage participants to suggest potential interventions (stimulated by the data visualisation) and note their ideas (UoM, S4B).</p> <p>The Manchester Ideas page on the LOOPER platform will be launched in mid-October (CL, UoM) and an offline version will be prepared for circulation to Brunswick residents--and the results transferred online (UoM, S4B).</p> <p>Issue based workshops will be organised with experts concerning solutions for air quality, traffic management and green infrastructure in order to discuss potential interventions that residents may be interested in testing (UoM, S4B).</p> <p>A community co-design workshop will be organised with residents and will include projection of 360° photos of areas of concern, which can be viewed through 3D glasses. Participants will be able to draw or write things about the interventions they favour and we will attempt to incorporate the changes into a modified 3D photo available online for further input (CL, UoM, S4B).</p> <p>We will organise a Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis (MAMCA) workshop in late November to evaluate alternative solutions with the necessary stakeholders (UoM, S4B, MCC). Brief preliminary interviews will be conducted with stakeholders beforehand to establish the criteria by which they will judge the alternative solutions (UoM). A set of possible interventions determined by the co-design process to date will be uploaded to MAMCA software (UoM).</p> <p>The MCA process will subsequently be completed. (UoM)</p> <p>A consensus-building workshop to finalise the choice of interventions to be implemented will follow in early December. (UoM, S4B)</p>	Oct. – Dec. 2018
Implementation of measures and monitoring (Learning Loop 1)	<p>Establish group of champions for each intervention (made up of residents and other stakeholders). We hope these champions will play key roles in implementation and monitoring and in outreach to others (UoM, S4B).</p> <p>Establish implementation partnerships for each intervention with key stakeholders who can support the implementation through either funding or expertise (UoM, S4B, MCC).</p> <p>Actual implementation of solutions (UoM, S4B, MCC).</p> <p>Develop a relationship with TfGM in preparation for potential interventions related to traffic. We have had a small amount of interaction with some TfGM staff concerning the annual Clean Air Day (held in June) and might consider</p>	Dec. 2018 – May 2019

	<p>aligning an intervention with it but the timing is not ideal as our interventions fall in between the 2018 and 2019 events (UoM, S4B).</p> <p>Engage with initiatives that reflect the type of interventions we might expect to implement in order to test these out on a small scale and develop relationships/lay the groundwork (UoM, S4B, MCC). Examples:</p> <p><i>The MCC Active Streets initiative</i> where we supported a street closure and creation of a temporary play area on 1 August 2018. The MCC organiser also asked us to monitor air quality in the area during the previous week and on the day of the road closure.</p> <p><i>A citizen-led initiative for installation of five demonstration Green Shed Roofs.</i> UoM Social Responsibility funding was accessed for the purchase of appropriate plants for the roofs. Builders involved in Brunswick regeneration are providing support in the form of salvaged construction materials and technical support. Others, such as City of Trees have also offered advice.</p> <p>Establish a monitoring group for each intervention that will involve residents and other stakeholders in the monitoring of the intervention. In terms of monitoring there might be a QR code and link to leave feedback. Volunteer monitors could do surveys of passersby and monitor traffic speed (UoM, S4B).</p>	
<p>Scoping of problems with first loop interventions (Learning Loop 2)</p>	<p>Monitoring of Learning Loop 1 interventions (UoM, S4B).</p> <p>Informal discussions with residents through community groups (UoM, S4B).</p> <p>Updating of secondary data (UoM).</p>	<p>June – Aug. 2019</p>
<p>Participatory data collection and visualisation (Learning Loop 2)</p>	<p>Analysis of data collected on interventions by monitoring groups (UoM).</p> <p>Visualisation of data through LOOPER platform and offline methods (UoM, IAUV).</p>	<p>Sept. – Nov. 2019</p>
<p>Co-design and evaluation of alternative solutions (Learning Loop 2)</p>	<p>Workshop with intervention champions and implementation partners to co-design amendments to interventions and potentially second iterations of interventions (UoM, S4B).</p>	<p>Dec. 2019 – Feb. 2020</p>
<p>Implementation of measures and monitoring (Learning Loop 2)</p>	<p>Actual implementation of Learning Loop 2 solutions (UoM, S4B).</p> <p>Monitoring of Learning Loop 2 solutions (UoM, S4B).</p>	<p>March – May 2020</p>

6. PROCESS - EVALUATION

6.1. Evaluation of each intervention

We will use the below template to collect basic information about the different interventions taking place in the Manchester LOOPER Lab, including how their impacts will be monitored and the learning that is expected to occur.

The template consists of a title, a photo, a 100 word summary, and four tables as follows:

1. Basic Information

This table is intended to capture a complete description of the intervention in terms of what and where it is, who is doing it, and how it is being funded.

<i>What is the intervention?</i>	Brief description of the physical or social changes that are being made
<i>Where is it?</i>	Grid reference
<i>How large an area does it cover?</i>	Approximately
<i>What is the duration of the experiment?</i>	Length of time the intervention is monitored
<i>What problems does it respond to?</i>	List key issues identified by community
<i>How/why was this intervention chosen?</i>	Key elements in co-design process leading to this choice
<i>How much funding is required?</i>	If funding is required state how much

2. Partner details

This table lists the different organisations that are involved in the intervention and their roles.

<i>Partner name</i>	<i>Role in intervention</i>	<i>Funded / in-kind contribution</i>
Name of partner (organisation, community group etc.)	Role played by partner (coordination, hosting, expertise, monitoring etc.)	Any monetary or in kind contribution

3. Monitoring plan

The monitoring plan will be coproduced with the community and partners to generate impacts and identify appropriate indicators together, and enrol community members in the monitoring process. Monitoring should reflect what partners want to learn about. This table captures the expected impacts that partners hope to achieve and the way in which these will be monitored.

<i>Expected impact</i>	<i>Ownership of impact</i>	<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Monitoring framework</i>	<i>Responsibility</i>
What are the expected / desired impacts from the intervention? These should be co-produced with the partners and communities involved.	Which partner wants to monitor this impact?	Indicator, units and dataset. Indicators should be adopted from frameworks in Appendix 1 to ensure consistency and align current best practice.	Sampling frequency, equipment required	Which partners will be doing the monitoring? Which will be coordinating it?

4. Learning

This table lists the different stakeholders who may be able to learn from the results of the intervention, and the ways in which their learning will be supported and evaluated.

<i>Stakeholder</i>	<i>Intended learning</i>	<i>Method to support learning</i>	<i>Evaluation of learning</i>
The stakeholders could include the community, local politicians, transport planners and so forth.	What will the stakeholder do with the learning? This could include new policies, capacity to tackle local problems, behaviour change and so forth.	How will LOOPER support this learning? For example, this might involve involving a transport body in the design of the intervention.	When and how will this stakeholder group's learning be evaluated?

6.2. Evaluation of the lab as a whole

In accordance with D4.2, we will evaluate our LOOPER Lab using three units of analysis: (1) 'activities' (including encounters with citizens/local residents or other stakeholders; data collection activities; and any other activities related to the Lab); (2) 'stages' of the Lab cycle (or 'learning loop') and of each of the interventions tested in the final stage; and (3) the overall 'Lab' and its impact on the neighbourhood, on policy, and on other stakeholders.

Co-produced evaluation We will strive to co-produce our evaluation with LOOPER participants as detailed in D4.2.

Data gathering: In addition to quantitative measures, we will make extensive use of observation, interviews and small group discussions. We will record our Lab activities and our observations in a logbook.

Formative Evaluation: We will use formative evaluation (usually through informal discussions within our team, which will be captured in our logbook) to answer questions like: Are our approaches to engaging local residents effective? Our answers to these questions will guide our subsequent actions i.e. we will continue using approaches that we have seen to be successful and change those that are not.

Summative Evaluation: We will complete our analysis of the quantitative and qualitative data that has been collected from the Labs overall in order to answer the evaluation questions we have set ourselves as listed in the D4.2 worksheets.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1

LOOPER = Learning Loops in the Public Realm

The LOOPER project is about learning together and trying out ways to make things better in the public areas of a neighbourhood (all of the areas that are open to everyone). These areas include parks and public buildings, as well as streets and other paths through the neighbourhood. These public areas are very important for the life of a community. They are also sometimes a source of conflict when people disagree about what should happen in a particular area and how other people should behave there. Some might think there is too much traffic or that people are driving too quickly, or that there is too much noise or not enough good play areas for children

During the next two years LOOPER project participants from the Brunswick neighbourhood and the University of Manchester will move through a number of learning loops. Within each learning loop we will try out new tools and we will learn new things, which we hope will lead to positive change in the Brunswick neighbourhood based on the ideas of people who live here.

LOOPER Stages

We will try to find out how Brunswick residents feel about the neighbourhood and what they might like to change. We will then try to learn more about the issues that people raise in order to fully understand them. For example, if some people say they are worried about air pollution and the effects on health, we can monitor the air quality in different parts of the neighbourhood and find out about common local health problems. Once we understand more about the problems, we can think about possible solutions. Together we can design some potential solutions and try them out. This will probably mean physically changing something in the neighbourhood on a temporary basis. Once we make the change, we can watch what happens to see if our experimental solution works. If it does work, we can try to make the change permanent.

Everybody in Brunswick is invited to get involved in LOOPER. Please let us know if you would like to be contacted about LOOPER activities or in playing a key role in the project. LOOPER offers opportunities to learn new skills and try out new technologies and to learn from the experiences of neighbourhoods in Belgium and Italy that are also involved in the LOOPER project.

We look forward to learning with you! Please contact janice.astbury@manchester.ac.uk

Updated last section 27 April 2018:

Brunswick residents who have participated in the process to date have expressed concerns about the following issues: air quality; traffic volume and safety; improving community spaces; greening the neighbourhood; and feeling safe and secure. We are now trying to learn more about these issues. For example, as many people say they are worried about air pollution and the effects on health, we will be monitoring the air quality in different parts of the neighbourhood. Once we understand more about the problems, we can think about possible solutions. Together we can design some potential solutions and try them out. This will probably mean physically changing something in the neighbourhood on a pilot or temporary basis. Once we make the change, we can watch what happens to see if our experimental solution works. If it does work, we can try to scale up and/or make the change permanent. **LOOPER offers opportunities to learn new skills and try out new**

technologies and to learn from the experiences of neighbourhoods in Belgium and Italy that are also involved in LOOPER (see loopproject.eu). We look forward to learning with you!

Please contact Janice janice.astbury@manchester.ac.uk for information about how to get involved.

Appendix 2

How do you feel about places in Brunswick?

<input checked="" type="radio"/> The place I like most Where?	Why?
<input type="radio"/> The place I like least Where?	Why?
<input type="radio"/> The place I am worried about Where?	Why?
<input type="radio"/> The place I want to change Where?	How?

Issues I am interested in or concerned about: (please tick appropriate boxes)

<input type="checkbox"/> Air quality	<input type="checkbox"/> Improving community spaces
<input type="checkbox"/> Traffic volume and safety	<input type="checkbox"/> Greening Brunswick
<input type="checkbox"/> Good routes for walking and cycling	<input type="checkbox"/> Feeling safe and secure

Other:

Please contact me about working on these issues.	Name: Email or telephone:
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Appendix 3

LOOPER Participatory Monitoring in Brunswick

Would you like to learn new skills and try out new technologies?

The LOOPER process involves learning together and trying out ways to make things better in the public areas of the neighbourhood (all of the areas that are open to everyone).

[Looper stages as in Appendix 1]

Brunswick residents who have participated in the process to date have expressed concerns about the following issues: **air quality; traffic volume and safety; improving community spaces; greening the neighbourhood; and feeling safe and secure.** We are now trying to learn more about these issues. One way is through monitoring the situation using new technologies. **We have monitors that measure air quality, noise and traffic speed** linked to online platforms where information can be recorded in maps and graphs so that we can understand what is going on in Brunswick and compare it with our partner neighbourhoods in Belgium and Italy. Then we can decide what to do about it!

Are you **interested in learning how to use these gadgets** (and possibly even making one of them)? Would you like to **be part of a team collecting data in the neighbourhood and analysing it?** Would you be interested in **becoming a local expert on important current issues and thinking about how to address them?** Please contact Janice janice.astbury@manchester.ac.uk to get involved.

Appendix 4

September is monitoring month for the LOOPER project

Hello!

As you've had contact with the LOOPER project you probably know that we've been monitoring air quality and other issues of concern. We are doing this more intensively in September and we're hoping you will join us.

We want to complete the monitoring this month so that we can then move on to thinking about which solutions to try—and we hope you will be part of that discussion as well.

There are several ways to participate in the LOOPER monitoring month:

(1) You can join Sharon and/or Janice on monitoring walks—one of us will be going out with air quality and traffic monitors almost every weekday in September during peak traffic times.

We will be covering Grosvenor Street, the areas close to the Mancunian Way, Brunswick Street, around Medlock School—and anywhere else you think we should.

If you are interested in this, please respond to this email so we can arrange when and where to meet.

(2) If you have a computer or smart phone, you can add your concerns and ideas to an online map by going to the website www.crowdmapping.eu/looper.manchester and then scrolling down the page to the photo of Manchester city hall. Click on the photo and enter the following information in the appropriate boxes.

[Username] Resident

[Password] September18

and then click on LOGIN

and then on INSERT

You are then ready to add things to the map. It is a bit difficult to get started with it so please don't hesitate to get in touch with us and we can give you some training. We can also lend you a smartphone to do it.

(3) If you have other ideas about information that should be gathered in order to think about how to address problems in the public areas of the neighbourhood, please let us know and we can discuss how to do this with you.

We hope to hear from you soon! (and please pass this on to anyone else you think might be interested)

Janice (janice.astbury@manchester.ac.uk) and

Sharon (Sharon.Thomas@S4Bmanchester.co.uk)

Appendix 5

Join the LOOPER project for traffic monitoring in Brunswick!

Are you concerned about traffic safety and/or air quality in Brunswick? Is there too much traffic moving through the neighbourhood? Are drivers going too fast? Are there particular problem areas? Join us to share your views and find out more at one of these times:

- Monday 24 September 3-4 pm (focused on school run)
- Tuesday 25 September 4-6 pm
- Thursday 27 September 3-4 pm (school run) and 4-6 pm

This is what we'll measure and analyse:

- Vehicle speeds
- The number of cars, lorries, motorcycles, bicycles and pedestrians travelling on specific streets
- Areas in need of interventions to improve traffic safety or air quality

We will have expert assistance from our LOOPER Brussels colleague!

Would you like to get involved?

Meet us in front of Brunswick Church at the start of one of the above time slots. If you are interested but not available at these times, please contact Janice Astbury at the below email.

Questions? janice.astbury@manchester.ac.uk